

DEVELOPMENT OF A WATER SOFTENING METHOD THAT ENSURES EFFECTIVE CLEANING OF HARDNESS SALTS AND INORGANIC COMPOUNDS IN TECHNICAL WATER

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Abstract: in the article, the amount of technical water currently used in oil fields, the quality composition of technical water, the analysis of existing methods used in water softening, scientific developments on the improvement of water softening technology based on modified sodium dodecylbenzenesulfonate chitosan were proposed.

Аннотация: мақолада хозирда нефт конларида фойдаланилаётган техник сув миқдори, техник сувнинг сифат таркиби, сувни юмшатишда қўлланаётган мавжуд усуллар таҳлили, модификацияланган натрий додецилбензолсулфонат хитозани асосида сувни юмшатиш технологиясини такомиллаштириш бўйича илмий ишланмалар таклиф қилинди.

Аннотация: в статье рассмотрены объемы технической воды, используемой в настоящее время на нефтяных промыслах, качественный состав технической воды, проведен анализ существующих методов, применяемых при умягчении воды, предложены научные разработки по совершенствованию технологии умягчения воды на основе модифицированного хитозаном додецилбензолсульфоната натрия.

Key words: oil fields, technical water, technical water composition, hardness salts, inorganic compounds, energy consumption, technical water softening methods.

Introduction: Today, the amount of technical water used in oil fields is on average 8 million cubic meters per year. Due to the presence of hardness salts and inorganic impurities in the composition of this technical water in excess of the established amount, scale forms in technical devices, which leads to excessive energy consumption and overheating of metal surfaces. Therefore, in order to prevent scale formation in devices, reduce energy consumption and overheating of metal surfaces, it is urgent to conduct research on methods for softening technical water.

Methods: The temperature of the reagents and the modified sorbent during application is 15-25 °C, humidity is (45÷75) % [1]. The experimental studies were conducted in accordance with ГОСТ ISO 10523-2017 [2], which is the requirements for the method for determining water quality and pH, and ГОСТ 30465-97, which is the requirements for the hardness and quality of water used

for industrial and household appliances [3]. In the first stage, the amount of calcium (Ca^{2+}) ions was reduced from 61 mg eq/l to 15.2 mg eq/l by means of reagents added to the technical water. In this case, 100 mg of soda ash (Na_2CO_3) was added to the sample and the pH was adjusted to 12.0 [4-5]. Then it was left for 2 hours. The precipitate was separated from the liquid phase, and after the first stage, the amount of calcium ions was measured. In the second stage, it was carried out by using a modified sorbent. In this case, water was softened from hardness salts and impurities and the following results were obtained (Table 1):

Results:

Table 1

Results of water softening from hardness salts and compounds

Parameter	Concentration, mg eq/l		Level of cleaning, %
	In the first water	In water after complex treatment	
Ca^{2+}	61,0	0,18	99,7
Mg^{2+}	7,16	-	99,9
Sr^{2+}	6,45	0,01	99,7
Mn^{2+}	7,16	0,01	99,8
Fe^{3+}	35,1	-	99,9
Cu^{2+}	7,49	-	99,9
Pb^+	3,68	-	99,9
Ag^+	5,30	-	99,9
Sn^{4+}	6,3	-	99,9

The quality composition of technical water used in oil fields was initially Calcium (Ca^{2+}) 61.0 mg eq/l, Magnesium (Mg^{2+}) 7.16 mg eq/l, Strontium (Sr^{2+}) 6.45 mg eq/l, Manganese(II) (Mn^{2+}) 7.16 mg eq/l, Iron(III) (Fe^{3+}) 35.1 mg eq/l, Copper(II) (Cu^{2+}) was 7.49 mg eq/l, Lead(I) (Pb^+) 3.68 mg eq/l, Silver (Ag^+) 5.30 mg eq/l, Tin(IV) (Sn^{4+}) 6.3 mg eq/l. After applying the developed water softening method, the degree of purification (in percentage terms) resulted in a decrease in Calcium 99.7%, Magnesium 99.9%, Strontium 99.7%, Manganese(II) 99.8%, Iron(III) 99.9%, Copper(II) 99.9%, Lead(I) 99.9%, Silver 99.9%, Tin(IV) 99.9%.

The development of a new modified sorbent composition used in the second stage sorption step is of great importance. A graphical representation of these results is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Graphic representation of the results of softening water from hardness salts and impurities.

Discussion: In conclusion, the two-stage method of softening technical water - the use of a reagent and a modified sorbent - has shown high efficiency. Calcium, magnesium and other metal ions are reduced by 99.7–99.9%. This approach prevents the formation of scale in devices, reduces energy consumption and meets the requirements of standards. It has been proven to be an effective and economical solution suitable for use in local conditions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that the creation of such methods, which are very necessary for Uzbekistan and the countries of Central Asia, is one of the urgent problems that cannot be postponed. However, European countries also face the problems of developing effective methods for technical water purification (for example, - Water Softening Using Reactors Loaded with Granular Materials, developed by the American Water Works Association). Our scientific research work has proven that we have the opportunity to develop a method for softening technical water that meets the requirements of European, Uzbek and Central Asian standards. In this regard, this scientific research work has proven that we have the opportunity to develop a new composition of reagents and modified sorbents to accelerate the process of softening technical water and produce methods that meet the requirements of state standards. It would be expedient to conduct these studies on an industrial scale.

List of used literature:

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